

How Scientific Computing, Spatial Data Science, Open Science, and Open Data Help Revitalizing Hard-to-reach Population: Evidence from a Decade Research on Taiwan Indigenous Peoples

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Summary

Based on scientific computing, spatial data science, and open science, this research demonstrates how open data (including spatial & attribute data) helps revitalizing hard-to-reach populations (HRPs) using Taiwan indigenous peoples (TIPs) as example. Scientific computing methods and high performance computing technologies, spatial data science, and open science are three crucial dimensions that are utilized to overcome challenges in processing, extracting, enriching, managing, and sharing information embedded in rapidly growing big archival data sets. Legal and ethical issues are a top priority in this research. The research demonstrates the automated data processing procedures of building open spatial & attribute data sets that enable us to revitalize regional development.

KEYWORDS: Hard-to-reach population, Open Data, Open Science, Scientific Computing, Spatial Data Science

1 Introduction

Hard-to-reach populations (HRPs hereafter) refer to those who are hard to access due to geographical location or/and social status. They are characterized by being vulnerable, excluded, and hidden in a society. The ability to access HRPs enables us to build insights into various issues they encounter and thus help us to design effective policy measures. Recruiting hard-to-reach populations has long been a big challenge for study. There are various barriers relevant to recruiting hard-to-reach populations. The most crucial challenges are: how to (1) label the population for study; (2) overcome mistrust of participants when reaching HRPs; (3) overcome legal and ethical issues to protect HRPs privacy and confidentiality.

Scientific computing methods and technologies, spatial data science, and open science are three crucial dimensions that are utilized to overcome the aforementioned challenges in terms of processing, extracting, enriching, managing, and sharing information embedded in rapidly growing big archival data sets. Using archival data to study indigenous peoples is a good example. Although indigenous peoples are small in population size, their crucial role of in different settings of societies and states around the world has long been recognized. Indigenous peoples are recognized as the preservers of global human diversity in the context of ecology,

biology, traditional knowledge, culture, and languages. One crucial barrier that still deeply hampers efforts towards the preservation and revival of indigenous peoples' diversity is the lack of state-of-the-art in-depth data on indigenous peoples.

2. Spatial data science, Open Science, and Open Data

There are three elements we need to highlight to distinguish the inter-relationship between spatial data science, open science and open data. The simplest but most informative is the one that defines spatial data science as a scientific framework that consists of three necessary components: (1) hacking skills, (2) advanced mathematics and statistical knowledge and skills, and (3) domain knowledge expertise. Spatial data science is based on real world domain knowledge expertise and refers to the extraction of knowledge from data, with the main goals of enhancing human knowledge from data and producing data products. It employs techniques and theories within the broad fields of mathematics, statistics, and information technology, including signal processing, probability models, machine learning, statistical learning, computer programming, data engineering, pattern recognition and learning, visualization, uncertainty modeling, data warehousing, and high-performance computing.

The calls for “Open Science” emerge due to the flaws of “Closed Science”, e.g., issues of scientific reproducibility, and access to data and knowledge systems. One important feature in open science is “replicability” and “reproducibility” given the same methods and data. However, there have been rising concerns in academic communities about scientific replicability and thus research credibility issues in the past few years. One result is the call for open science. By definition, open science is the movement to make scientific research methods, data, and results accessible to all communities. Open science consists of six principles: open data, open source, open methods, open peer review, open access, and open educational research. Using TIPD (<https://osf.io/e4rvz/>) as an example, the research demonstrates the automated data processing procedures in building open data. The transformed new sets of data must fit two criteria: first, they must preserve the main features and most information embedded in raw data; second, they must resolve privacy, confidentiality, and thus legal issues; third, they must comply with academic research ethical requirements. With such issues resolved, the built data sets fit the criteria of open data and thus can be utilized directly by the research team members.

3 Data and Methods

There are various challenges in coping with big data. The main source of data utilized to construct TIPD is Taiwan Household Registration (THR) administrative micro data. In terms of data integration, repository, and sharing, the research adopts the following simple but effective methods. At first, open data integration is achieved by batch processing on a local computer. The research makes use of Dropbox and Google Drive as data repository platforms for the integrated open data sets. The contents of TIPD on Dropbox and Google Drive are always identical to each other through a standardized process of data synchronization with a local data repository. Hardware infrastructure does matter and plays a very crucial role in constructing TIPD, particularly in scientific computing for probabilistic record linkage. In-memory high performance computing is crucial to the research. It comprises three kernel skills of manipulating digital infrastructure: (1) overclocking CPUs, (2) overclocking internal memory speed, and (3) accelerating I/O bus bandwidth that links CPUs and internal memory. The programming codes are designed for in-memory computing purpose in the sense that all computing tasks of

constructing the human relationship and kinship databank are implemented in the computer's internal memory, with CPUs and internal memory being overclocked, and the I/O bus between CPUs and memory being accelerated.

The research thus moved geocoding system from TAMS to Google's geocoding system in late 2016. However, Google system imposes many restrictions in address geocoding, e.g., limitation on the number of addresses which can be geocoded. To overcome this constraint, the author develops a method in late 2018 that allows us to make voluminous address geocoding by parsing Google Map information in automated batch mode. The author continues to improve this new geocoding method and it now works smoothly without any problem. As a result, the research finally achieves to re-locate more than eighty million individual archives from 2007 to 2022, with each individual's latitude and longitude information being recorded in WGS84 projection coordinate system. Using digital terrain model (DTM), the corresponding altitude information for each pair of latitude and longitude is also collected in address geocoding archive.

4 Concluding Remarks

With scientific computing, spatial data science, and open science as foundation to build open spatial data, the research achieves the following goals that may contribute to open science: (1) designing a data enrichment process that allows us to construct open data in an automated and consistent way by using high-performance computing digital infrastructure; (2) reorganizing raw data as open data to overcome legal and ethical issues based on the foundation of distributed storage methods; (3) allowing us to enrich data through the process of data integration methods, making longitudinally linked data (including both exact and probabilistic record matching) less expensive and more efficient; (4) enabling us to go further to extract very detailed information from raw data, such as the construction of micro genealogies, identity, and ethnic marriage patterns.

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Appendix Figure

Hard-to-reach Population Studies: A Multidisciplinary Research in Scientific Computing, Data Science, and Open Science

(1) Scientific Computing Data model

(2) Data Science, Open Science, and Open Data

TIPD on OSF

TIPD on IEEE DataPort

(3) Spatial Science & Geocoding

Population distributions

Migration flows

Communities

(4) Record Linkage and Spatial/Temporal Dynamics

Population dynamics

Genealogy

Migration dynamics and trajectories

(5) Micro-to-macro Approach and Predictive Analytics

Micro-to-macro link framework

Neural network & ML

TIPD

<https://osf.io/e4rvz/>

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